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THALASSEMIA

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ABSTRACT

Thalassemia is an autosomal recessive disorder. It occurs due to defect or mutation in the chromosome -11. There are several types of thalassemia which causes severe anemia with sometimes chronic heart failure. They are several types of hemoglobin are there causing a thalassemia. The allogenic bone marrow transplantation and the local drugs plays a promising role in the treatment of thalassemia.

Keywords: *thalassemia, local drugs, allogenic stem transplantation, oral deferiprone, subcutaneous desferoxamine.*

INTRODUCTION

Thalassemia, sickle cell disease, hereditary spherocytosis are a group of inherited disorders of hemoglobin synthesis. Thalassemia is the ubiquitous diseases in the worldwide. Thalassemia occurs due to the defect or reduction in the globin protein present in the hemoglobin. The body does not get sufficient RBC and due to insufficient production of erythropoiesis leads to thalassemia. The factors include genetics, $\alpha 2$ polypeptide depression, $\beta 2$ polypeptide depression and family history.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Local drug like oral deferiprone or subcutaneous desferoxamine prescribed for a bronze diabetes of a thalassemic major. Cytotoxic therapy have increased the Hb-F synthesis. Several agents such as hydroxyurea, cytarabine, butyrate analogs are

stimulating the Hb-F production in thalassemia patients. Iron overload is one of the main causes and it results in thalassemia. There are several types of thalassemia include thalassemia major ,thalassemia minor , thalassemia intermedia and α thalassemia. First hemoglobin to develop GOWER-1 followed by GOWER -2 then produces Portland Hb-F (fetus) produced in 14 weeks in liver and spleen. Around 38 weeks in bone marrow Hb-A (Adult) appears chipmunk faces will be seen in thalassemia major patients. Hepatosplenomegaly, severe hemolytic anemia, X-ray squaring of the metacarpals will be seen, frontal / maxillary prominence are the manifestations and features of the patients having thalassemia disease.

RELEVANCE

Thalassemia has a chronic hyper coagulant state. There is a chance of occurrence of venous and arterial thrombo-embolus after splenectomy. The reasons for the procoagulant effect is erythrocyte membrane abnormalities.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

To develop an awareness to minimize the thalassemia diseases and to educate the peoples to diagnose early especially for fetus to avoid unnecessary complications.

METHODOLOGY

The drug delivering system for treatment of thalassemia are oral deferiprone, subcutaneous desferoxamine. If that is not possible in some cases switch to allogenic bone marrow transplantation. Somatic therapy experiment is still on research.

RESULT

Inflammasome in erythropoiesis to treat anemia . To prevent thalassemia after genetic counselling and to warn the risks of intra marriage. Amniocentesis, Chronic villus sampling, prenatal diagnosis will help them to diagnose and prevent the

disease. 1000 Bone marrow transplants have been performed and achieved in the patients for disease free survival rate of 80% to 90% .

REFERENCE

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